

**ANALYSIS AND FORECASTING OF FINANCIAL RISKS OF GERMAN
ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF UNPREDICTABLE PRICE
DYNAMICS OF ENERGY RESOURCES**

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Abstract: *The relevance of this topic is due to the fact that at present in Germany there is an unpredictable price dynamics of energy resources, changes in interest rates, the dynamics of the euro exchange rate, and is also due to such factors as the instability of the political situation and the changing principles of state influence in the financial sector.*

Purpose of the work: to study the economic impact of financial risk on the German financial system, to explore methods for measuring, identifying and managing financial risks at the company level.

Research methodology. In the course of the study, such modern methods of studying economic phenomena and processes as a dialectical approach, system analysis, formal logic, statistical research techniques were used.

Keywords: *Analysis, forecasting, financial risks, enterprises, price dynamics, energy resources*

Introduction

This paper discusses the economic essence of risks, methods for their analysis and forecasting, as well as methods for managing financial risks. Risk and crisis management in an enterprise is one of the most important functions of financial management, since in the absence of proper management of these categories, enterprises usually go bankrupt and cease to function. Therefore, a thorough study of financial risks is the most relevant topic today in the context of business management in Germany.

If we take into account the fact that such detrimental consequences can occur with many enterprises, then this will lead to a deterioration in the situation on a macroeconomic scale, since with a decrease in sales and financial results, income tax payments are reduced for economic agents, there is a reduction in personnel, which with one On the other hand, it means a loss of income of the population and a decrease in demand, and on the other hand, it means a decrease in tax deductions (from salaries) and, in addition, due to a drop in demand, budget revenues from indirect taxes are reduced. As a result of such events, there is a reduction in private and public consumption/investment and a fall in German real GDP. For an individual entrepreneur, the motivation for introducing a high-quality mechanism for managing financial risks is to prevent a decrease in the economic efficiency of the enterprise and eliminate factors that threaten the existence of the enterprise.

The research methods

The following scientific research methods were used in the work: measurement, comparison, modeling, observation, induction and deduction, axiom, analysis and synthesis.

The object of the study is a German company specializing in the performance of work on insulation and finishing of facades, on its example, methods of analysis, risk forecasting, as well as certain measures of anti-crisis management will be considered.

A fairly large number of organizations go bankrupt due to inefficient management. In this case, the main measures for the financial recovery of such organizations are the reconstruction of management procedures in order to find ways and opportunities to use, first of all, on-farm reserves. To develop specific measures at different stages of recovery, you can use various options for management actions that are most typical for most organizations. In the system of financial

recovery of the organization, first of all, it is necessary to widely use internal reserves of financial stabilization.

This is due to the fact that their successful application allows not only to remove the financial threat of bankruptcy, but also to a large extent rid the organization of dependence on the use of borrowed capital, accelerate its recovery at lower costs.

In international financial practice, the effect of operating leverage is denoted by DOL (**Degree of Operational Leverage**) and implies that any change in sales revenue (Sales) generates a stronger change in earnings before taxes and interest (EBIT, Earnings Before Interests and Taxes).

Formula:

$$\text{DOL} = \frac{\Delta \text{EBIT}\%}{\Delta \text{Sales}\%},$$

ИЛИ

$$\text{DOL} = \frac{\text{Sales}-\text{VC}}{\text{Sales}-\text{VC}-\text{FC}},$$

Where VC are variable costs, and FC are conditionally fixed (non-financial) costs

Based on the above formula, we can conclude that the higher the share of fixed costs, the higher the level of operating leverage. The higher the level of operating leverage, the higher the uncertainty in forecasting future cash flows, since a relatively small deviation in terms of sales can cause a significant deviation from expected cash flows. This implies that the higher the level of operating leverage, the higher the riskiness of cash flows (which causes both uncertainty in future returns for investors and increases the risk of financial stability, due to the fact that slight market fluctuations can significantly reduce cash flows and cause insolvency) and the lower the market value of the shares.

The riskiness of cash flows is one of the three criteria for assessing the real value of shares according to Eugene Brigham, the other two criteria are the amount of cash flows and the interval of cash flows.

To assess the total risk DTL (Degree of Total Leverage) of entrepreneurial activity, the combined value of the financial leverage DFL (according to the American approach) and the operating leverage DOL are used in order to determine the sensitivity of taxable profit (EBT, Earnings Before Taxes) from changes in sales income (Sales).

Formula:

$$\text{DTL} = \text{DFL} * \text{DOL},$$

OR

$$\text{DTL} = \frac{\Delta \text{EBT}\%}{\Delta \text{Sales}\%}$$

For an example of calculating the total leverage, let's take the conditional data of a conditional enterprise.

Sales revenue (Sales)	35 000 000
Variable Costs (VC)	10 000 000
Fixed (non-financial) expenses (FC)	15 000 000
Interest expenses on a loan (Interests)	5 000 000

Step 1 Calculate DOL:

$$\text{DOL} = \frac{\text{Sales}-\text{VC}}{\text{Sales}-\text{VC}-\text{FC}} = \frac{35\,000\,000-10\,000\,000}{35\,000\,000-10\,000\,000-15\,000\,000} = \frac{25\,000\,000}{10\,000\,000} = 2,5$$

Step 2 Calculate DFL:

$$\text{DFL} = \frac{\text{EBIT}}{\text{EBIT}-\text{Interests}} = \frac{35\,000\,000-10\,000\,000-15\,000\,000}{35\,000\,000-10\,000\,000-15\,000\,000-5\,000\,000} = \frac{10\,000\,000}{5\,000\,000} = 2$$

Step 3 Calculate DTL:

$$\text{DTL} = \text{DOL} * \text{DFL} = 2,5 * 2 = 5$$

According to the total leverage, it can be concluded that with a change in sales income by 1 unit, a change in taxable income by 5 units will follow.

Such cumulative leverage is dangerous, on the one hand it is certainly a possibility, since with an increase in sales income by 20%, taxable profit will increase by 100%, but with a fall in sales income by 20%, the company will be on the verge of profitability, and with a drop in sales more than 20%, the company will begin to suffer losses.

One of the logistic regression models is the James Olson model. The O-Score model is based on the same approach as Altman's, however, the author uses statistics for two thousand companies, which ultimately gives a more accurate model with nine variables. According to the Olson logit model, the indicator (T) is calculated using the following formula:

$$T = 1,32 + 0,407SIZE_t + 6,03(TL_t/TA_t) + 1,43(WC_t/TA_t) - 0,0757(CL_t/CA_t) + 2,37(NI_t/TA_t) + 1,83(FFO_t/TL_t) - 0,258X + 1,72Y + 0,521[(NI_t - NI_{t-1})/(|NI_t| + |NI_{t-1}|)]$$

where,

SIZE - Natural logarithm of the ratio of total assets to the deflator index of gross domestic product (GDP);

TL - Total Liabilities;

TA - Total assets;

WC - Working capital;

CL - Short-term liabilities;

CA - current assets;

NI - Net profit;

FFO - Net Income + Depreciation;

X - 1 if the company is unprofitable in the last two periods, 0 in all other cases;

Y - 1 if $TL > TA$, 0 otherwise.

t - reporting period;

t-1 - previous period.

|NI| - net profit taken modulo.

The rating coefficient T is used to find the probability of bankruptcy using the logistic regression formula:

$$R = 1/(1+e^T)$$

where,

R is the probability of bankruptcy (in fractions of one);

e is the base of the natural logarithm (Euler number, $e = 2.71828$);

T - rating coefficient calculated according to the Olson model.

Let's conditionally calculate the probability of bankruptcy of German companies using Olson's Logit model

$$SIZE - \ln(28\,561\,569 / 1,075) = 17,1$$

$$TL - 15\,048\,510;$$

$$TA - 28\,561\,569;$$

$$WC - 25\,011\,941 - 15\,048\,510 = 9\,963\,431;$$

$$CL - 15\,048\,510;$$

$$CA - 25\,011\,941;$$

$$NI - 2\,591\,541;$$

$$FFO - 2\,591\,541 + 196\,241 = 2\,787\,782;$$

$$X - 0;$$

$$Y - 0;$$

Step 1 Calculate the value of T according to the received data:

$$T = 1,32 + 0,407 * 17,1 + 6,03 * 0,527 + 1,43 * 0,349 - 0,0757 * 0,602 + 2,37 * 0,091 + 1,83 * 0,185 - 0,258 * 0 + 1,72 * 0 + 0,521[(2\,591\,541 - 2\,395\,503)/(2\,591\,541 + 2\,395\,503)] = 1,32 + 6,96 + 3,178 + 0,499 - 0,046 + 0,216 + 0,3385 + 0 + 0 + 0,02 = 12,4855$$

Step 2 Calculate the bankruptcy probability R:

$R = \frac{1}{(1+e^T)} = \frac{1}{(1+2,71828^{12,4855})} = 0,0000037811 < 0,5$; значит вероятность банкротства крайне низкая (0,0004%) исходя из условных расчетов по модели Олсона. [27]

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that financial risks are inherent in any economic system with market relations due to the fact that the market is in a state of permanent uncertainty. There are two types of risks by origin:

1) objective 2) subjective. Objective risks are risks that arise in the external environment and the economic agent is not able to influence them. Subjective risks are risks arising within individual economic entities, which entities can influence. Even the most effective risk and crisis management department will not be able to eliminate objective risks, the task of the relevant managers is to regularly monitor the activities of the company's departments and make decisions to minimize and, ideally, eliminate subjective risks: production risks, marketing risks, personnel risks, accounting risks that in essence, it all boils down to the ultimate financial risk. Objective risks cannot be avoided, but they can be foreseen in order to prepare a package of anti-crisis measures in advance and thereby reduce their detrimental impact, which is also the most important task of the risk and crisis management department.

2) In fact, the methods presented in this study are a tool for identifying weaknesses in an enterprise with the help of appropriate calculations and help to understand at what stage of the crisis the enterprise is, whether there is a crisis at all and what situation can be provoked. The methods for assessing the risk of the onset of the final stage of the crisis (liquidation) were also touched upon. That is, based on these methods, it is possible to analyze and predict financial risks.

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